

Addendum to the description of the new species *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* Wallach, 2020 (Serpentes: Typhlopidae)

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INTRODUCTION

The formal description of a blindsnake from Thailand, *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* was proposed by WALLACH (2020a) to correct the confusion that resulted from an accidental publication of the name in a thesis by NIYOMWAN (1999). The data presented for the species, cited then as *Typhlops ozakiae*, was believed by subsequent authors to have fulfilled the requirements of the third edition of the *Code* (ICZN, 1985) for publication and availability. However, use of the name was not intended as the description of a new species since Niyomwan believed that it had already been published by Wallach when it was actually a manuscript name. Furthermore, it did not conform to Articles 8, 11 and 13 of the *Code* (ICZN, 1985), therefore making it a *nomen nudum*. Over the next two decades the taxon was treated as a valid species in publications under the name of *Ramphotyphlops ozakiae* and, subsequent to HEDGES et al. (2014), as *Indotyphlops ozakiae* (see WALLACH 2020a for complete synonymy). As in the case of *Virgotyphlops* (WALLACH 2020b; FRÉTEY & DUBOIS, 2021), the author was unaware of the 2012 amendments to the *Code* (ICZN, 2012a-b), explicitly discussed in detail by DUBOIS et al. (2013), regarding electronic publication of new names at the time he described *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* (WALLACH, 2020a). This publication will assure that the name *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* is available under the *Code*.

SYSTEMATICS

The failure to preregister the name with ZooBank is now being corrected with this online publication, which has been registered in ZooBank as urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:238703EA-6C8F-466F-8C7C-4E98F5D1E516.

Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae is being proposed again, this time with a 2021 publication date. All previous references to *Typhlops ozakiae*, *Ramphotyphlops ozakiae*, *Indotyphlops ozakiae*, and *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* are unavailable and technically anoplonyms or, more precisely, atelonyms *vide* DUBOIS & FRÉTEY (2020). A compilation of the above names in synonymy is summarized in WALLACH, 2020a.

Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae sp. nov.

Holotype: FMNH 180007.

Type locality (emended): Sakaerat Experimental Station, Udom Sap, Wang Nam Khiao District, Nakhon Ratchasima Province, Thailand (14.510250°N, 101.930805°E, elevation 385 m).

Paratypes: FMNH 18003–06 and ZMUC R52174.

Etymology: Named in honor of Molly Ozaki (1927–2010), Administrative Assistant and Secretary in the FMNH Division of Amphibians and Reptiles for 15 years (1978–1992).

Vernacular name: Molly's blindsnake.

Diagnosis: *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* can be distinguished from all other species of *Ramphotyphlops* and *Indotyphlops* as described in detail in WALLACH, 2020a. Briefly, *R. mollyozakiae* is most similar to *R. albiceps* and can be separated by its postoculars (1 vs.

2–4). From *R. lineatus* it can be recognized by midbody scale rows (20 vs. 22–24) and from all other *Ramphotyphlops* species with 20 scale rows it is separable by the superior nasal suture (visible on the dorsum of the snout vs. not visible). It can be distinguished from *Virgotyphlops braminus* and *Indotyphlops violaceus* by the inferior nasal suture contact (supralabial 2 vs. preocular). Among *Indotyphlops* species with 20 scale rows it can be identified by a lower number of total middorsals in comparison with *I. pammeces* (< 327 vs. > 328), *I. porrectus* (< 330 vs. > 400), and *I. schmutzi* (< 330 vs. > 385). It is separable from *I. malcolmi*, *I. tenebrarum*, and *I. veddae* by the nasal shield (divided vs. entire). *Ramphotyphlops mollyozakiae* can be separated from *I. jerdoni* by its postoculars (1 vs. 2) and from *I.*

lankaensis by its higher number of total middorsals (> 290 vs. < 265).

Distribution: Southeastern Thailand and Sumatra, Indonesia, 385–1000 m.

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LITERATURE

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